

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Seifu****FIRST NAME: Tesfaye****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: Six****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MS Word 365, Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the following should you not do when paraphrasing?

- Restate information and ideas accurately.
- Change just one or two words in a sentence.¹**
- Use your own language and style.
- Reference the source.

2. Choose the correct notes- bibliography style of citation for the following source of information.

- **Source: A Book written by Shoshanah Cohen and Joseph Roussel**
- **Title of the book: Strategic Supply Chain Management: The Five Core Disciplines for Top Performance**

¹ Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1.*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 8.

- **No. of pages: 298**
 - **Publisher: McGraw- Hill**
 - **Year of publication: 2013**
- Cohen, Shoshanah and Roussel, Joseph. 2013. “Strategic Supply Chain Management: The Five Core Disciplines for Top Performance”. 298 pages. New York, McGraw-Hill.
- Cohen, Shoshanah and Roussel, Joseph. 2013. *Strategic Supply Chain Management: The Five Core Disciplines for Top Performance*. New York, McGraw-Hill.
- Shoshanah Cohen and Joseph Roussel, Strategic Supply Chain Management: The Five Core Disciplines for Top Performance. (New York, McGraw-Hill, 2013).
- Cohen, Shoshanah, and Joseph Roussel. *Strategic Supply Chain Management: The Five Core Disciplines for Top Performance*. New York: McGraw-Hill, 2013.²**

3. Which one of the following does not describe the characteristics of WHO reference style?

- Name of all authors is listed when there are three or fewer.
- When there are four or more authors, the first author’s name written “et al.” is added.
- Name of journals is written in full.
- Italicize the titles of journals and put titles of books in a quotation mark.³**

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff., Eighth edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 91.

³ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 25.

4. Which one of the following sentences is wrong?

- The paraphrase you use must look very different than how the author originally wrote it.
- The writing style you use to express the author's ideas must be similar with the style the author used.** ⁴
- Use quotations when an authority figure says something that can help you persuade the reader.
- A serious academic offense that can have serious consequences.

5. Given the following conditions listed from A-D, which of the following qualitative approaches are selected for the given conditions respectively?

- A. Collect participant's story or capture a group of participants stories and retell**
 - B. Develop an explanation that helps in understanding of phenomenon**
 - C. Explore a phenomenon by studying a group of people or individual**
 - D. Capture participants experience and examine how they make sense of their experiences**
- Case study, grounded theory, ethnographic approach, and phenomenological.
 - Narrative, grounded theory, ethnographic approach, and phenomenological.** ⁵
 - Narrative, grounded theory, ethnographic approach, and case study.

⁴ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5–7.

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End* (Los Angeles, London: Sage Publications, 2008), 11.

- Narrative, ethnographic approach, grounded theory, and phenomenological.

6. Which one of the following is mismatched with respect to American vs British writing styles?

- Nigeria has played well in the match, even if it lost. – American.
- He said, "I didn't like what they had for dessert." – British.**⁶
- 14th March 2016 – British.
- Standardize – American.

7. Which of the following research paradigm, genre of inquiry, research purpose, and research design corresponds to qualitative research approach respectively?

- Post positivist, correlational, seek consensus, and deductive.
- Critical theory, ethnography, seek variation in finding, and inductive.**⁷
- Constructivism, case study, investigate relationships, and inductive.
- Pragmatic, correlational, seek consensus, and hypothetic- deductive.

8. Which one of the following is not true about storyboard?

- Storyboard is an outline spread over several pages.
- All reserches need to have a storyboard.**⁸

⁶ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1.*, 27–35.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 13.

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 22.

- Storyboard states research questions and working hypothesis.
- Storyborad allows adding new hypothesis.

9. What are the three core elements of an argument in a research?

- Research problem, reason, and evidence.
- Claim,warrant, and evidence.
- Claim, reason, and evidence.**⁹
- Research problem, questions, and purpose.

10. Which choice shows the correct format for the first in-text citation to refer for a concept taken from page 52 of the following journal article:

- “Seifu, Tesfaye, Asres, Kaleab and Gebre-Mariam, Tsige. 2006 “Ethnobotanical and Ethnopharmaceutical Studies on Medicinal Plants of Chifra District, Afar Region, Northeastern Ethiopia”. Ethiopian Pharmaceutical Journal 24: 41-58.”**
- (Seifu, Tesfaye, Asres, Kaleab and Gebre-Mariam, Tsige. 2006: 41-58).
 - (Seifu, Tesfaye, Asres, Kaleab and Gebre-Mariam, Tsige. 2006: 52).**¹⁰
 - (Seifu, Tesfaye, Asres, Kaleab and Gebre-Mariam, Tsige. 2006).
 - (Seifu, Tesfaye et al., 2006:52).

⁹ Turabian, 37.

¹⁰ Turabian, 130.

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Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End*. Los Angeles, London: Sage Publications, 2008.

Gulma, Kabiru, and Cleenewerck Laurent. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Eighth edition. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.